

Tracking soil biodiversity in response to soil tillage

Problem

Soils are vital substrates for growing crops, and provide habitats for soil-dwelling organisms. Soil management and crop type affect soil biodiversity by influencing habitat quality and resources for soil organisms. Soil organisms contribute to a range of soil functions that support agricultural productivity, yet soil cultivation disturbs the soil environment and exposes soil organisms to stress and predation. Methods to monitor soil biodiversity can help land managers decide which practices are best suited to preserve soil biology and the soil functions it supports.

Solution

Earthworm abundance, type and activity was assessed as an indicator of soil biological diversity in winter grain crops drilled directly into uncultivated soil compared with ploughed soil.

Benefits

Earthworms are a characteristic component of soil biodiversity and earthworm activity improves soil structure, drainage and organic matter incorporation. Assessing earthworm abundance and activity provides an indirect measure of how these soil functions change in response to soil management, crop type and agricultural inputs.

Applicability box

Theme

Soil management
Soil function
Soil health indicators

Keywords

Soil cultivation
Soil biodiversity

Context

Scotland

Application time

Autumn (pre-sowing) to summer (harvest and post-harvest)

Required time

An annual crop growing season

Period of impact

Between 1-5 years of annual growing cycles

Equipment

Spade, bags, white sheet, tub

Best in

Arable cropping

Practical recommendation

- Soil should be sampled using a sampling design that covers different areas across the field (e.g., AHDB recommends walking a 'W' pattern across the sampling area).
- In dry soil, worms will migrate to deeper layers, and it is recommended to take samples when soil is moist (e.g. after a period of rain).
- Samples can be collected pre-sowing, during crop growth and after harvest. It is important to take samples at the same time of year in each year of sampling, as soil indicators can vary within the season.
- A 20 x 20 cm quadrat is placed on the ground at each sample location (**Figure 1A**), and the number of middens and wormcasts is counted.
- After scraping away the surface litter/debris, a 20 x 20 x 20 cm soil pit is dug out and the soil placed onto a white surface (**Figure 1B**). The soil is hand sorted to remove worms; these are transferred to a pot to count the number of juveniles and adults (**Figure 1C**).

Figure 1. Sampling soil for earthworms. (A) locating a quadrat onto the soil surface, (B) digging a soil pit, (C) extracting and counting juvenile and adult worms (Gill Banks)

- The number of adults in each functional group can be recorded using an earthworm identification guide (see further information). After counting, the worms are returned to the soil pit.
- In winter barley and winter oilseed rape fields sampled in July and August, juveniles accounted for >85% of the worms detected in soil samples. Worm abundance was highest in oilseed rape fields and tended to be higher in unploughed (zero till) soils (**Figure 2**).
- Worm activity (middens, wormcasts) varied considerably between fields and there were no strong patterns in relation to worm abundance or soil management, which likely reflects variability in worm presence in shallow versus deep soil layers in response to soil conditions (moisture, temperature).

Figure 2. Worm numbers detected in 20 x 20 x 20 soil pits, averaged across nine (Aberdeenshire) or ten (Angus) loci per field, in response to winter barley or winter oilseed rape sown into ploughed or undisturbed soil.

Further information

Further reading

Karley AJ, Banks G, Brandt J, Swyst I, Mitchell C, Hawes C, Boldrin D, Loades K, Ndlovu T, Zuta A, Begg G. 2025. Impact of zero tillage winter grain crops on soil health indicators. Summary report of farm trials in 2024 for the RESAS project B3-1 Co-designing and implementing best-fit farming practices. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15728881

Weblinks

Check these resources for more practical recommendations.

Earthworm guide: https://csc.hutton.ac.uk/resource/Handbook_of_indicators_v1.pdf

<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/action-plan-for-soil-testing>

<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/how-to-collect-a-soil-sample>

About this practice abstract

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